

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

W8013S, a promising thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) line for two-line system hybrid rice breeding

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W6154S, which is thermosensitive, was derived from the original Hubei photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile rice Nong Ken 58S. The fertility of W6154S can be greatly altered by temperature variation during fertility induction. Its use in hybrid seed production is therefore limited.

We tried to breed new TGMS lines that have lower critical temperature for fertility restoration than W6154S (25.2 ± 1.0 °C). W8013S is such a TGMS line.

W8013S, derived from the cross W6154S/Xie Qing Zhao//Xie Qing Zhao, has japonica-type cytoplasm and indica-type nuclear background. It is photoperiod-insensitive (see table).

W8013S flowers in Wuhan 58-93 d (CV = 8.6%) after a late Mar to late Jul sowing. It has a mean cumulative effective temperature of 1244.6 °C (CV = 11.0%)

We observed that the stable male sterile period in W8013S was from 2 Jul to 16 Sep. During this period, a 99.5–100% abortive pollen rate and almost zero seed-setting rate under natural light/temperature conditions occurred. Day length or theoretical light length (12–14 h) affects its sterility very little.

Correlation analysis was made on the abortive pollen rate at heading and each of the nine temperature components including daily air temperature, water temperature, and soil temperatures at 0, 5, 10, and 20 cm beneath the surface 7–22 d before heading.

The most closely correlated component was the soil surface temperature occurring 12-16 d before heading. This means that the thermosensitive stage in W8013S

Fertility test and analysis of fertility response in TGMS lines. Wuhan, China, 1990.

Material	Abortive pollen rate ^a (%)			Type	Thermosensitive stage ^b	<i>r</i> value ^c	Index of critical temperature (°C)
	LD	SD	<i>t</i>				
W6154S	99.69	98.97	1.67	TGMS	12–15	0.507–0.707**	25.2 ± 1.0
W8013S	99.36	98.86	0.79	TGMS	12–16	0.556–0.746**	24.4 ± 0.9
W6111S	99.90	99.88	0.20	TGMS	11–14	0.775–0.835**	25.5 ± 1.1
NK58S (check)	99.98	27.93	12.57*	PGMS			

^a LD = 16 h light + 8 h dark. SD = 10 h light + 14 h dark. Treatments were from the midstage of the first rachis-branch primordium differentiation to heading; mean air temperature ranged from 26.6 to 30.5°C. ^b The *i*th day before heading. ^c ** = significant difference at P < 0.01.

remains when the pollen mother cells undergo meiosis. By doing further regression analysis using the abortive pollen rate of 99.5–100% as the eligible index, we obtained a critical temperature (24.4 ± 0.9°C) for its fertility alteration (see table). The index is obviously lower than that for W6154S and other TGMS lines.

Higher temperature (*t* ³ 25.3°C) induces completely sterile pollens; lower temperature (*t* = 23.0–25.2°C) induces

fertile ones. Lower critical temperature is necessary for producing hybrid seed during the higher temperature seasons. The extremely low temperatures in mid-summer 1989 were a good test for stability. W6154S and some other TGMS lines became partially fertile, but W8013S was still highly sterile.

Extensive testcrossing of indica and japonica varieties and screening of F₁ crosses are under way to exploit the breeding potential of W8013S. □

Buli-INIA, the first fine-grain rice variety released in Chile

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Low temperatures at seedling and flowering stages are a major constraint in rice production in Chile. Japonica rice, such as Oro and Quila, with bold, short or medium grains and a high degree of white belly has traditionally been grown in Chile. But consumer

preference is changing.

INIA released Diamante in 1979. It has long, translucent grain, but its eating quality did not meet the new standards of Chilean consumers who prefer high-quality imported rices, such as Bluebelle.

INIA and CIAT began a collaborative research project in 1984 to develop germplasm that combines cold tolerance, earliness, and good grain quality. Buli-INIA, a semidwarf with translucent, long, slender grain, is the first variety to come from the joint venture. It was selected from a cross between Lemont/Quila 66304 and Diamante. Both Quila 66304 and Diamante are early and cold tolerant.

Some agronomic and grain characteristics and yield of Buli-INIA and check varieties from regional trial data during 3 growing seasons (1988–91) in Chile.

	Plant ht (cm)	Days to flowering ^a	Milled rice				Yield (t/ha)		
			Length: width	White belly ^b	1,000-grain wt (g)	Amylose ^c (%)	1988–89	1989–90	1990–91
Buli-INIA	82–97	96–124	3.3	0.2–0.8	26.0	20.6	7.0	5.6	7.1
Diamante-INIA	89–114	93–118	2.9	0.4–1.0	33.0	21.6	7.9	6.1	6.8
Oro	97–103	84–115	1.7	4.2–4.8	32.0	20.6	8.3	6.2	6.7
Quila-INIA	84–115	84–115	1.8	1.4–4.3	30.0	20.6	7.0	6.7	6.4

^a Dependent on planting date. ^b Scored on scale of 0 to 5: 0 = clear, translucent grain, 5 = chalky grain. ^c Determined in IRRRI laboratory.